

A research on Factors affecting to the pronunciation of first-year English-majored students at HUFU

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Abstract

Pronunciation might not be the most important factor in language learning, pronouncing well is still important, even early on in the learning process. How is it affect major English students at the Ho Chi Minh University of Food Industry is important to understanding students then has a good method to teach and learn more effectively. Using a questionnaire on 30 freshmen English-major at Ho Chi Minh City University of Food Industry. The result of this questionnaire can show what factors affect the pronunciation of the first-year English major-students. With the outcome this research found, the students and teachers can have a lot of benefits for improving the way of teaching and learning. It shows what kind of difficulty or advantage that students have to deal with or receiving when they communicate.

Keywords: pronunciation; first-year students; communication

1. Introduction

For many years, the final purpose of English learning or language learning in general is to use the language for communicating with others in daily life or works. Before the learners want to have good communication they must have comprehensible pronunciation as Morley (1994) said 'The learner wants to have good communication they must be correct their pronunciation first'. A question is how others could understand completely the information which incorrect pronunciation. They might be miss understand and got trouble in responding to the information that they received. However, in Vietnam pronunciation is not as important as grammar or vocabulary. The instructors often pay attention to grammar then the learners might have good grammar but then the learner cannot use that grammar for communication because they cannot pronoun the right sound of the word. Since a long time ago, many researchers were doing a search on this aspect to find out the way to solve this problem and help the learners to improve their pronunciation or the quality of their communication. They point out specifically the difficulties that the learners might have trouble with as "Difficulties in the Pronunciation of English Sounds by Asian Speakers" Beng (1985), or showing how is it be like when they have a good pronunciation as Vesna (2017) said in her research "A study of proper pronunciation as a factor of successful communication". The primary aim of this study is to offer suggestions for teaching or learning English pronunciation by showing the difficulty of pronunciation that HUFU freshmen students have to deal with. This aspect is not new but it necessary to doing a research on specific learners as HUFU freshmen students. The outcome of this research may help both teachers and learners to find a way to improve their teaching or learning.

2. Literature review

For many students of a second or foreign language, the essence of spoken language proficiency is often perceived to be good or native-like pronunciation. Finding a language teacher who would agree with them may have been a problem for those students during the 1980s. This world where the teacher or the program ignored current fashion trends, the pronunciation course materials would typically have reflected an essential structuralism perspective (isolated sound segments, each identified contrastively, and memorization exercises) Yule (1989). In recent years, people start to pay attention to pronunciation more than the past but it still has a low percentage. The most reason for the instructor is to create their students who can pass the exam and not underrate whether they can utilize what they learn in real-life or not. They might not know or care much about the significance of elocution. Dalton said that the teaching of pronunciation plays a crucial role in second language learning has become an integral part of almost any language course and with good pronunciation is indeed indispensable for adequate communication in a foreign language and is, moreover, to a large extent responsible for one's first impression of a learner's L2 competence. He also points out that the importance of pronunciation teaching is even more strikingly obvious in the context of language teaching at the university level, which involves the training of future language teachers (Dalton-Puffer et al., 1997).

At the point when you converse with individuals in reality, your elocution is the main thing they notice during a discussion. In regular correspondence, you typically don't need to utilize many confounded words, so your restricted jargon is anything but a major issue since you can utilize increasingly straightforward words to communicate the word that you don't have the foggiest idea. Truth be told, they will see immediately if your articulation is fortunate or unfortunate just the initial not many straightforward words. If the speakers have a poor pronunciation with the exceptionally solid outside highlight, they will consider you a terrible English speaker and your great jargon and punctuation can't support you. Pronunciation is not only 'listen and repeat. Pronunciation incorporates highlights of language includes speaking, listening, vocabulary, and grammar. Like vocabulary and grammar, pronouncing by seeing and getting rules and examples which lie underneath the outside of discourse. For instance, if an English word has two syllables, the pressure is as a rule on the principal syllable for things and descriptors, and the second syllable for action words (LLE, 2018). It is difficult for individuals who hear it out with your solid remote complement. It is aggravated for others on the off chance that they need to continue requesting that repeating, however, the receiver despite everything can't make sense of what you are stating. Thusly, on the off chance that it takes a ton of endeavors to comprehend learners English, individuals will abstain from speaking with you as much as could be expected under the circumstances. Conversely, they will appreciate conversing with learners when they have a wonderful compliment that is simple to hearing and get you.

Since English is utilized in different settings by different speakers everywhere throughout the world, it follows that the elocution varies altogether and the deviation of the 'right' or standard articulation has occurred generally. Since the focal point of the postulation is the right English pronunciation, People ought to get acquainted with the real significance of the term 'pronunciation' just as with the careless divisions of English. However, what many people are doing here may appear as an endeavor to impeccably duplicate certain pronunciation. There are numerous individuals among people who may talk with various sounds English is the official language utilized in the English talking nations like Great Britain, the United States, Australia, and New Zealand or a few conditions of Africa (Phra Sinphasith Chatapanyo, 2016). Notwithstanding, the motivation behind the English language utilization doesn't lie exclusively

in its official job however is somewhat alluded to as the subsequent language or unknown dialect because of the expanding number of nonnative English speakers. Recent research has highlighted the benefits of choosing intelligible accented speakers as pronunciation models rather than native speakers of English (Murphy, 2014). These models might be simpler to mirror because of an assortment of elements, for example, a slow discourse rate, the comparability in physical appearance, and models apparent as being feasible—not "great." Such models are especially useful for development in delaying, the utilization of unmistakable quality, and the utilization of non-verbal correspondence to depict trust in communicating in a second language.

1. Do motivation & attitude affect pronunciation?
2. Does age & exposure affect pronunciation?
3. Does mother-tongue (Vietnamese) affect pronunciation?
4. Does natural ability affect pronunciation?

3. Method

This research is using a survey to study the factors that affect the pronunciation of fresh-man HUFU English-majored students.

a. Participant

The participant of the research is the fresh-man HUFU English-majored students who have just come from high school to university. A freshman in school is otherwise called a first-year student. It is the primary year of a school profession and it is another period of their life. Approaching green bean understudies that start school directly after completing secondary school are commonly 18 or 19 years of age. As freshmen, students for the most part experience a few changes since they are living new encounters, meeting new individuals and they may be away from home for the first time of life. They are new to step into a new area of the high level of English. They must be confused about the difference in the curriculum that won't like what they thought.

b. Sampling procedures

Selecting 20 students and 4 students from each class to fill up the survey. Each participant has a different level of English to show the objectivity of the result.

i. Material & Research Instrument

Consulting on A Study of Factors Affecting EFL Learners' English Pronunciation Learning and the Strategies for Instruction by Abbas Pourhosein Gilakjani. And the result of the Google Form (A survey administration app that is included in the Google Drive office suite along with Google Docs, Google Sheets, and Google Slides. Forms feature all of the collaboration and sharing features found in Docs, Sheets, and Slides). Google Forms is an instrument that permits gathering data from clients through a customized study or test. The data is then gathered and naturally associated with a spreadsheet. The spreadsheet is populated with the overview and test reactions.

4. Results

The study set up a hypothesis that motivation & attitude, age & exposure, mother tongue, and natural ability affected the results of pronunciation. Based on the multiple-choice in the

questionnaire, the data were collected and analyzed statistically as shown in 4 tables. The scores were in the rank follow the order of strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, strongly agree.

a. *Do motivation & attitude affect pronunciation?*

In this chart, almost (70%) of candidates agree and 10% of candidates strongly agree with motivation & attitude could affect pronunciation. The rest (20% left) who choose neutral or disagree with this statement.

b. *Does age & exposure affect pronunciation?*

This second table has shown 75% of candidates who agree with age & exposure could affect pronunciation. There are 10% of candidates strongly agree with the statement while it's just 5% of candidates disagree. Also, there are 10% of candidates chose neutral.

c. *Does mother-tongue affect pronunciation?*

In this third table, there are (65%) agree with mother-tongue could affect pronunciation while there are just 5% of candidates disagree and 7% neutral. Especially, there are 25% of candidates strongly agree with the statement.

d. Does natural ability affect pronunciation?

Almost all candidates (80%) agree with natural ability could affect pronunciation. More than that, there are 10% strongly agree while it's just only 5% disagree and 5% neutral.

5. Discussion

According to 4 tables above, the majority fresh-man HUFU English-majored agreed with 4 factors (motivation & attitude, age & exposure, mother-tongue, natural ability) effect to their pronunciation. Motivation & attitude (table1) has 70% agree and 10% strongly agree. For some individuals, it's difficult to complete something when they couldn't care less. Excellent pronunciation is frequently influenced by inspiration. This is true that the students didn't care about it, they will presumably not improve a lot. This is especially obvious when the students arrive at a level where individuals can get them. When they are not fathomable numerous students lose interest in further elocution advancement. With the age & exposure (table 2. 75% agree) more youth students, particularly 1-12 years old, have the most obvious opportunity at creating pronunciation like a native. If the students are older, they will quite often hold their

"accent" and can't change it. Exposure is firmly identified with age. The more credible encounters that the students have with the language the better their pronunciation is. For the mother-tongue effect (table 3. 65% agree, 25% strongly agree), The similitudes between the native-language and the objective language can impact pronunciation. For instance, it is a lot simpler to move from Vietnamese to English pronunciation than from Japan to English. Last but not least, natural ability (table 4. 80% agree & 10% strongly agree) some simply get it while others don't. Various students have shifting capacity to get the hints of another dialect. A path around this is helping students to know their weaknesses and strengths. This will help them to create a way to improve.

6. Conclusions

The research on factors affecting the pronunciation of first-year English-majored students at HUFU has contributed to the methodology for learning or teaching pronunciation in Ho Chi Minh City University Food of Industry. The result has shown three factors that affected the pronunciation of freshman HUFU English-majored student's motivation & attitude, age & exposure, mother tongue, and natural ability. There are a few circumscribe in this research as a sample number, common field, and the accuracy of the data. However, the students could have many benefits when they read this research because they will find the best way to improve their pronunciation and the teachers could have a different strategy to design their lesson and could focus more on pronunciation. Since this research, the researchers can dive into a specific phone in which students at HUFU have the most trouble when producing the sound and help them.

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